

D9.1 Quantity of Access Offered - TA2

Version 1.0 (*final*)

Date 23 December 2022

Grant Agreement number: 823914

Project acronym: ARIADNEplus

Project title: Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe - plus

Funding Scheme: H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1

Project co-ordinator name, Title and Organisation: Prof. Franco Niccolucci, PIN Scrl - Polo Universitario "Città di Prato"

Tel: +39 0574 602578

E-mail: franco.niccolucci@pin.unifi.it

Project website address: www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Horizon 2020 Programme (H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1) under grant agreement n° 823914.

Author:	Nicky Garland Archaeology Data Service, University of York
Quality control	Sheena Bassett, PIN Paola Ronzino, PIN

Document History

- 02.12.2022 – Draft Version 0.1
- 12.12.2022 – Draft Version 0.2
- 15.12.2022 – Quality control
- 18.12.2022 – Final version 1.0

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons CC-BY License. To view a copy of the license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	5
2	Introduction and Objectives	6
2.1	About the Transnational Access Training Programme	6
2.2	Ensuring the quality of candidates	6
2.3	Data Stewardship	7
3	TNA Dissemination, evaluation and offers	8
3.1	The first TNA Call	8
3.2	The second TNA call	9
4	Candidate projects	11
4.1	First TNA Call - Data Stewardship (2020).....	11
4.2	Second TNA call - Data Stewardship (2022)	12
5	Overview of training provided	15
5.1	First TNA Call - Data Stewardship (2020).....	15
5.2	Second TNA call - Data Stewardship (2022)	16
5.2.1	Data Stewardship School Programme.....	17
6	Evaluation and conclusions	19
4	Annexes	21
	Guidelines for TNA Evaluators	22

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the Trans National Access (TNA) activities carried out during the ARIADNEplus project within Work Package 9 (WP9.1) by the Archaeology Data Service, University York, UK. This deliverable describes the aims and objectives of the training activities, the results achieved by this work package and a review of the feedback provided by the participants.

The training for the first TNA call was undertaken in February 2020, however, only some of the participants were able to attend. Due to the COVID pandemic the remaining participants were transferred to the second TNA call, which was announced in February 2022. The training activity for this call initially consisted of an online four-week Summer School between the 4th May to 1st June 2022. However, this training course was postponed due to the low number of participants.

The training activities were rescheduled in October 2022. Instead, an online Winter School programme was designed and delivered to suit the requirements of the participants. The Winter School programme was divided into four thematic sessions delivered over a four-week period from the 15th November to the 7th December 2022. The four thematic sessions included; Introducing the Archaeology Data Service, Data Management, Digital Preservation and Quality Assurance & Data Reuse.

In addition to the main schedule, two additional special events were presented by external speakers on topics of interest to the participants. These two events included a discussion of The Dig Digital online toolkit, developed by DigVentures in partnership with Chartered Institute for Archaeologists (CIfA), and the Community Owned Preservation Tools Registry (COPTR) tools as developed and curated by the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC).

Overall, ADS was able to deliver training to eight students in total (nine offers were made but one had to drop out at the last minute), fulfilling the target of seven accesses minimum. Following the training events, the project participants were asked to complete the TNA summary user report to provide feedback on the organisation of the Data Stewardship Schools and the quality of training delivered. The feedback from participants suggests that the participants were highly satisfied with the contents of the course and the resources produced and that the training had tangible benefits to both their projects and current positions.

2 Introduction and Objectives

2.1 About the Transnational Access Training Programme

The ARIADNEplus TNA Training Programme was originally planned as up to three annual calls for individual/team training for:

- Mapping Existing Datasets to CIDOC-CRM (at PIN, Prato, Italy), and
- Individual training: Data Stewardship (UoY ADS, York, UK).

The first of these calls was issued in September 2019 with visits by candidates planned for between January and June 2020. Subsequent calls were to be issued in 2020 and 2021 until the maximum capacity on each course had been reached. This was 15 user weeks (75 days) for PIN and 7 user weeks (35 days) for ADS.

Two further courses were offered as week-long Summer Schools by CNR, Pisa, Italy:

- Visual Media for the Documentation of Fieldwork and Artefacts, and
- Implementing Interoperability.

The Summer Schools were planned for 2021 with the expectation (based upon previous experience) that most of the places offered were likely to be taken up in one year but with the contingency that a second set could be offered in 2022 if not.

The global COVID-19 pandemic and national lock-downs severely disrupted the TNA Programme, however, as travel was restricted from Spring 2020. The situation only began to improve in 2021 with the roll-out of national vaccination programmes and reduced restrictions, which allowed people to start travelling again. Consequently, the programme was revised to allow as many researchers as possible to apply and attend. All training was offered as four Summer and Winter Schools between May and December 2022 with first priority given to previously accepted applicants who were unable to attend their original placements.

2.2 Ensuring the quality of candidates

To provide quality training, the students attending the TNA courses had to be suitably qualified and were undertaking relevant projects and research. Consequently, an independent panel of external experts was formed and the applications from each student were sent to a member of the panel for review and evaluation. The external evaluators were:

- Milica Tapavički-Ilić, Institute of Archaeology, Belgrade, Serbia
- Ivana Pandzic, University of Banja Luka, Bosnia Herzegovina
- David Bibby, Heritage Office, Stuttgart, Germany.

In addition, three senior ARIADNEplus members involved in the TNA delivery also received the applications and evaluations to ensure they agreed with the recommendations.

The three external evaluators were each provided with a set of guidelines (see Annex A) for performing this task, each returning a written summary for the candidates they were asked to assess.

2.3 Data Stewardship

The *Data Stewardship* activity was offered by the Archaeology Data Service, based at the University of York, as part of the TNA Training Programme.

During this activity ADS staff supported applicants by addressing differing levels of capacity around data management and stewardship and identified important issues to develop better data stewardship within countries and organisations. As part of the activity, a Data Stewardship TNA training programme was developed to introduce participants to current data management best practices for archaeological data and to help them apply these to their own situations. The training programme was developed and delivered by experts across the ADS, who provided guidance, support and expertise to participants in the application of these techniques to their own projects or organisations.

In addition to the formal training programme, the activity offered assistance to participants access to ADS specialists in order to evaluate the most appropriate data stewardship practices and approaches for their region, country or organisation. Utilising ADS expertise and facilities, the participants were able to examine and customise data stewardship for their specific requirements. During the training programme, participants were offered the opportunity to discuss different issues with ADS experts and to organise further meetings to discuss issues relevant to their personal or organisational requirements. These points of contact and expertise continue to be available to participants beyond the training programme and life of the ARIADNEplus project.

3 TNA Dissemination, evaluation and offers

3.1 The first TNA Call

The first TNA call was announced in September 2019 (<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/tna-2019-call-for-access-visits-pin-and-ads/>)

These training opportunities were as follows:

- Individual training: Mapping Existing Datasets to CIDOC-CRM (PIN)
- Individual training: Data Stewardship (UoY ADS)

The call was widely disseminated over Social Media (Twitter, Facebook) and through the partners own dissemination channels. A leaflet was also prepared and partners were asked to take these to events they organised or attended.

ARIADNEplus

Trans-National Access for Archaeologists

ARIADNEplus provides Trans-National Access (TNA) to archaeological researchers to enable them to create, manage, integrate and optimise their datasets and documentation and to participate in the use of research infrastructures. TNA is tailored to address specific research questions and projects for in-house placements and also provides training and support via two annual summer schools that cover the topics of dataset design and multimedia documentation.

In-house placements for individuals and small groups

In-house placements (normally one week in duration) are designed to give TNA participants support and training on the relevant activities needed for best practices associated with datasets:

- Mapping Existing datasets to CIDOC-CRM
hosted by PIN, Prato, Italy
- Stewardship and Curation of Archaeological Data
hosted by the Archaeology Data Service (ADS)
University of York, UK

Summer Schools

These week-long Summer Schools, hosted by CNR-ISTI, Pisa, Italy, are held June-July and aim at providing students with expert guidance and the skills and knowledge on the specific topics covered. Access to tools and services on-site help each participant progress with their specific project:

- Dataset Design & Management
- Visual Media for the Documentation of Fieldwork & Artefacts

How to apply

Calls will be made from September 2019 every six months until March 2022 inviting candidates to apply. All information and the online form will be published on the ARIADNEplus website:
<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/transnational-access>

Priority will be given to:

- users who have not previously used the ARIADNEplus resources
- young researchers
- researchers working in countries where no such research facilities exist

Each application will be reviewed by a Selection Panel who will recommend which candidates are to be offered places.

Successful candidates will be awarded bursaries to cover the costs of travel and subsistence.

Further information regarding the TNA content, eligibility and the application procedure are to be found on the website.

ARIADNEplus is a project funded by the European Commission under the H2020 Programme, contract no. H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1-823914.

@ARIADNEplus
www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

Figure 1. The TNA Leaflet

Application forms and information were provided on the ARIADNE Infrastructure website (<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/tna-2019-call-for-access-visits-pin-and-ads/>).

Data Stewardship (Archaeology Data Service, University of York)

Eight applications were received and sent to members of the external Evaluation Team for review and feedback. The results of the evaluations were as follows:

Name	Institute	Country
Solveig Steffen	DAI	Germany
Vera Moitinho de Almeida	INESCC	Portugal
Emilie Trebuchet	INRAP	France
Nicky Garland*	Newcastle University	UK
Humberto Aguilar	IDACOR	Argentina
Miguel Carrero	Uni. Santiago de Compostela	Spain
Martina Polig	CYI	Cyprus

*Nicky Garland was not eligible for a bursary but was accepted as a self-funded candidate.

One further application was also received but was not put forward for evaluation as it was incomplete and the applicant did not respond to emails requesting further information. Humberto Aguilar's application was rejected as the evaluation highlighted that his project and role did not appear to be connected to data archiving. Miguel Carrero's application was rejected for the same reason, the stated aim being "to get more expertise on database planning and management".

Unfortunately, only two of the candidates were able to attend their training courses before March 2020, the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic in Europe. These were Martina Polig, CYI and Nicky Garland, Newcastle University.

3.2 The second TNA call

The second TNA call for the Summer Schools was issued mid-February 2022 (<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/summer-schools-2022/>). These were as follows:

- Data Stewardship – ADS, University of York, UK. Online on Wednesdays 4th, 11th, 18th, 25th May and 1st June 2022.
- Mapping Existing Datasets to CIDOC CRM – PIN Scrl., Prato, Tuscany, Italy. Monday 20th–Friday 24th June 2022.
- Visual Media for the Documentation of Fieldwork and Artefacts – CNR, Pisa, Italy. Monday 27th June–Friday 1st July 2022.
- Implementing Interoperability – CNR, Pisa, Italy. Monday 4th–Friday 8th July 2022.

All four Summer Schools were promoted through the usual channels and also on the DARIAH Digital Humanities Course Register. At the same time, all the previously accepted candidates who had not received their training were contacted and asked if they would like to attend the corresponding Summer School instead.

Data Stewardship (Archaeology Data Service, University of York)

For the *Data Stewardship online Summer School*, there were only four applicants, two of which were transfers from 2020 call (Dr Solveig Steffan, Vera Moitinho Almeida), who couldn't undertake the training before the disruption caused by the COVID pandemic, as well as two new applicants (Georgina Barrett, Godefroy Devevey). Unfortunately, four candidates was not enough to justify the Summer School going ahead so this was rescheduled for the end of 2022 (November to December). At this point several other participants were also invited to attend the training including two placement students at the ADS. Due to changing working commitments, it was not possible for Georgina Barrett from the Museum of London to attend the training event. The ADS did provide access to training materials produced during the course.

For a full list please see the Winter School schedule (Annex 2).

Name	Institution	Status
Dr. Solveig Steffan	Stuttgart Regional Council	Confirmed (transfer from 2020)
Georgina Barrett	Museum of London	Confirmed
Godefroy Devevey	ICArEHB, Uni. Algarve	Confirmed
Vera Moitinho Almeida	University of Porto	Confirmed (transfer from 2020)

4 Candidate projects

This section provides a sample of the candidates' proposed projects as outlined in their application forms to illustrate the variety of applications being catered for and the specific interests covered.

4.1 First TNA Call - Data Stewardship (2020)

Para- and Metadata Databases for the Documentation of Cypro-Minoan Inscriptions - Matina Polig

The proposed project for the TNA training relates to my PhD project : 3D approaches to Cypro-Minoan writing, an undeciphered Bronze Age writing system from Cyprus. As part of my PhD project I am documenting and analysing approximately two thirds of Cypro-Minoan inscription corpus in 3D (ca. 180 objects). In the course of the documentation and analysis databases are being created that capture for each object information on :

- 3D data acquisition and post-processing pipeline
- Archaeological context and object properties (material, type, etc.)
- Inscription (number of signs, orientation, geometric properties, etc.)

The databases are used as support and guidance in the analysis of the 3D analysis and results, as documentation of the process, providing transparency and enabling data-reuse. A part of them will also be incorporated in a 3D online archive of the corpus at the end of the thesis.

The Hadrian's Wall Community Archaeology Project (WallCAP): The WallGIS (Geographical Information System) Database - Nicky Garland

WallCAP was a National Heritage Lottery Funded (NHLF) community archaeology project that engaged local communities and volunteers in the vital task of securing the heritage of Hadrian's Wall WHS for future generations. The project produced several digital outputs, which were centralised within a single management system; a Geographic Information System (GIS) for the entire Hadrian's Wall WHS, named the WallGIS.

The overall objectives of the WallCAP GIS project are as follows:

- To create a comprehensive database of archaeological sites within the Hadrian's; Wall World Heritage Site (WHS).
- To input data from all WallCAP fieldwork projects into the WallGIS.
- To ensure that data on all Scheduled Monument within the WHS are inputted into the WallGIS.
- At the end of the project to successfully archive the WallGIS with the Archaeology Data Service.
- To ensure the long-term management and use of the WallGIS.

4.2 Second TNA call - Data Stewardship (2022)

Digital long term archaeological Archiving of digital data from excavation and fieldwork - Dr. Solveig Steffan

Over the last years documentation of archaeological excavations from analogue plans and reports to digital data changed („born digital“). The change to deposition and securing of digital data according to the rules of archive standards has not yet been considered enough in Baden-Württemberg’s archaeology service. Guidelines for creation and transfer of this data have to develop further. Already today some data can no longer be opened, some with difficulties (e. g. unmigrated data). How should we deal with legacy data?

The necessity for appropriate procedures has generally been recognised and is reflected in job-growth over the last two years. In the last months, therefore, a basis for data management and administration of digital excavation data has come into existence. But a lot of work still needs to be done.

For example, the access and reusability of data: at present the data is simply deposited on an exclusive server, which gets backups on regular intervals. The data has neither uniform standards nor is it structured, saved or archived in a special way. Also, the access is very limited. Excavation areas are saved as GIS-Polygons are fed into an administration/research database, but with limited metadata. The data is available as a GIS-layer. Accessibility and reusability of the data must be improved.

The objective of the project is, as much as possible, to provide safe and long-term usable storage and administration of data from archaeological heritage according to recognised archival standards. Until now, as described above, just a simple storage of data on an external server and recording of limited metadata occurs. The aim is to provide better use, evaluation and re-use of research data in near future, but especially in mid to long term future. To reach this aim a development in the use of standards to better protect and re-use of data is needed; a real data service. Only then we will guarantee better handling for users, sustainability and data security. These standards shall include the archive worthiness of data and understanding archiving as an active process. We also need to educate depositors.

Implementing OS at the data-level with adequate data stewardship at the Interdisciplinary Center for Archaeology and Evolution of Human Behavior (ICArEHB) - Godefroy Devevey

My current position as scientific coordinator in a research center I will not describe a single research project, but instead a project that touches upon all current and future research projects within our centre.

ICArEHB is a human-size research centre (about 25 PhD holders) that is dedicated to prehistoric archaeology and the study of human evolution. The researchers are producing about 50 articles per year in international journals, all in Open Access since 2020. The centre has a good dynamic in terms of funding, recruitment, and research projects. For example, ICArEHB will initiate two ERC projects in 2022, and one in January 2023. Every year, ICArEHB receives several projects funded by national

public funders (FCT) and international foundations (e.g., the Wenner-Gren Foundation, Foundation Fyssen, National Geographic Society, Leakey Foundation). These projects are producing a considerable amount of data from new excavations, from new analyses, and also from re-analysis of existing but poorly documented collections. In addition, the centre has taken a strategic turn toward more workshops and collaborative synthesis. Altogether, ICArEHB is thus becoming a major node of production of data in prehistoric archaeology.

Some of our researchers (e.g., João Cascalheira) are already following the Open Science principles, with a systematic sharing of data and analytical scripts of each article on the Open Science Framework (www.osf.io). However, in the absence of a formal workflow and a properly trained officer in the house, these initiatives will remain anecdotal.

For this reason, my aim is to generalise the Open Access and FAIRing of all data produced by the researchers and projects of ICArEHB. My first objective is to be trained as a data steward to be able to better apprehend the different steps for adequate data management. With this training, I want to be able to support my researchers at two essential stages (objectives 2 and 3): a) at pre-data stage, to explain and support the elaboration of the data management plan for each project following the Open Science principles, and b) at post-analysis stage, to create an internal workflow to ensure that all data (empirical and analytic) produced by ICArEHB are FAIR.

Stewardship of digital archaeological data in ODEEG - Vera Moitinho Almeida

ODEEG (Online-Datenbank zur Erforschung der Entwicklung von Gefäßformen und -maßen) is an open-access online database for research on the development of ancient pottery shapes and capacities. It is specially focused on fine-wear painted vessels, from ancient Greek territories and Cyprus. Whereas the period encompasses 10th–4th century BCE, approximately from the Geometric period to the Hellenistic period. ODEEG is connected to the wider Corpus Vasorum Antiquorum (CVA) project - an international project for the documentation, standardised publication, and research of ancient Greek pottery, located in museums around the world. The oldest project of the Union Académique Internationale, dating back to 1919.

The objectives of the ODEEG project are manifold:

- (1) To digitally document ancient Greek and Cypriot fine-wear pottery in 3D in an accurate and standardised way;
- (2) To make different types of data available for researchers, via a dedicated open-access online database referencing to the Beazley Archive Pottery Database (BAPD);
- (3) To ensure long term digital preservation of the data.

At the end, we aim at providing a solid basis for distinct types of archaeological and other scientific research including, but not limited to, chronological and regional differentiation of vessel shapes, dimensions, and capacities; pottery manufacturing and function; ancient measuring systems; as well as knowledge, cultural, social, and economical networks.

Some of the potentialities of working with 3D digital data in archaeology are already well known (for a review see Moitinho de Almeida and Rieke-Zapp, 2017). The number of online databases providing open-access to 3D datasets and aggregators linking to 3D open data of CH objects for research has increased in the last decades: ADS (1996-), Aves 3D (2011-), Edition Topoi (Exzellenzcluster Topoi, n.a.), Europeana (2008-), MorphoBank (2012-), MorphoMuseum (Lebrun, Orliac, 2016), MorphoSource (2012-), Pelagios (2011-), Phenome10 K (Goswami, 2015), Zenodo (2013-), just to name a few. Concerning online databases with 3D models of ancient pottery, low resolution models are typically available, possibly mainly for fast visualisation purposes. However, crucial data, such as raw data, high-resolution data, and corresponding technical metadata – also for repeatability and reproducibility of the data, are much needed for a rapidly growing number of scientific works – seems to be overall neglected. The ODEEG project will help fill this gap, by providing a wide variety of meaningful and citable data for researchers via a dedicated open-access online database. Moreover, it includes a large number of born digital assets, with a special focus on 3D scanned data (including raw and post-processed data), but also photographs, automatic scientific illustrations, and corresponding archaeological and technical metadata. In order to exploit extra knowledge and provide more useful information, it also incorporates links to other datasets on the Web, namely, GeoNames (2005-), Chronontology (2016-), PeriodO (2014-), and the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT, 1998-). Linked Open Data (LOD; Berners-Lee, 2008) and FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) are applied. Digital resources are deposited and archived in ARCHE for long-term preservation. In this vein, the aim of this TNA is to analyse the data and discuss best practice solutions concerning Data Stewardship.

5 Overview of training provided

5.1 First TNA Call - Data Stewardship (2020)

Two participants were able to attend the first TNA placement in February 2020; Martina Polig and Nicky Garland. As such the Data Stewardship training was designed in order to address the specific requirements of the projects proposed by these participants. In reviewing each project it was ascertained that the following subjects would be suitable:

Martina Polig (Para- and Metadata Databases for the Documentation of Cypro-Minoan Inscriptions)

1. Identifying problems and issues with database
2. Interoperability between different databases
3. Relationships between database and other files/resources.
4. Documentation/metadata?

Nicky Garland (Hadrian's Wall Community Archaeology Project - WallCAP)

1. Long-term management of digital datasets.
2. To create protocols for the continued use and updates of the WallGIS beyond the life of the project.
3. To research and create protocols for data sharing between the WallGIS and county and national HERs.

A two-day course was designed and delivered in York, UK. Time was factored in for one on one interaction between ADS staff and the two training participants to address their specific needs. The training was delivered at both the ADS offices and the Council for British Archaeology offices.

Data Stewardship Programme

An outline of the two-day course is provided below:

Day 1 - Tuesday 25th February

10:00 Introductions

10:30 Introduction and the work on the ADS - Tim Evans (ADS)

11:15 Outline of project and outcomes from placement (Martina Polig)

11:35 Outline of project and outcomes from placement (Nicky Garland)

12:00 General discussion of data management and planning - Katie Green (ADS)

13:00 Lunch/move to ADS Office

14:30 Breakout groups on specific questions for Martina & Nicky

16:30 End

Day 2 - Wednesday 26th February

10:00 Interoperability and reuse (Tim Evans - ADS)

10:45 Standards, formats and guidelines (Kieron Niven - ADS)

11:30 Examination of specific issues for placements (Tim Evans and Kieron Niven - ADS)

13:00 Lunch/move to ADS Offices

14:30 Outstanding issues and data management planning (Tim Evans - ADS)

16:30 End

5.2 Second TNA call - Data Stewardship (2022)

As part of the second TNA, an online Summer School was designed and scheduled to be held in May and June 2022. However, this event was subsequently delayed due to the low number of participants. The training programme was rescheduled for November and December 2022 and renamed the 'Data Stewardship Winter School'. At the later date, a larger group of participants was recruited (which included students transferred from the previously cancelled Summer School):

Name	Nationality	Institution	Position
Godefroy Louis François Devevey	French	Universidade do Algarve	PhD researcher
Dr Vera Moitinho	Portuguese	Institute for the Study of Ancient Culture, Austrian Academy of Sciences	Post doctoral researcher
Dr Solveig Steffen	German	Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Baden-Württemberg	Archivist
Jonas Abele	German	Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Baden-Württemberg	Archivist
Georgina Barrett	English	Museum of London Archaeology (MOLA)	Archaeological Collections Manager
Jimmy Maranga	Kenyan	British Institute in Eastern Africa (BIEA)	Librarian
Sabina Batlle Baro	Spanish	University of Barcelona	PhD researcher

Following selection of the training participants, a period of consultation was undertaken to ascertain training needs and organisational requirements. To facilitate the choice of topics a list of possible sessions/topics was sent to each participant (see below). The ADS asked participants to rate each topic on their level of interest from 'no interest' to 'high interest'. These topics were based upon ADS expertise and general interest topics relating to data stewardship that were felt could be of interest to our participants. The participants were also offered the opportunity to add additional topics or questions that they would like raised during the training programme. A list of the topics is provided below:

Possible sessions/ topics for discussion
Introduction to the ADS History and Services
Attendee presentations - zoom presentations from participants on their personal/organisational requirements
Where to start: Knowing Your Data
Organising Your Data
Introduction to the ADS Guides to Good Practice
Selection and Retention Strategies
Introduction to Data Management Planning
Case study: Chartered Institute for Archaeologists (CIfA) Dig Digital Toolkit
Introduction to Thesauri and Standardised Vocabulary
The Importance of Metadata: Discovery and Preservation
Introduction to Digital Preservation
Migration and Normalisation of Files
Workflows for Archives
Tour of ADS archiving workflow (our bespoke collections management system and our preservation workflows)
Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) Community Owned Preservation Tools Registry (COPTR) tools
ADS Case study: Online Deposition Systems and Data Ingest (ADS-easy)
Quality Assurance (i.e. technical assurance of data formats/metadata as well as of archaeological data content)
ADS Case study: Monitoring data and data integrity (i.e. checksums, data validation tools etc)
ADS Case study: Where is our Data: Reaching for the clouds (i.e. data storage solutions)
Looking to the Future

5.2.1 Data Stewardship School Programme

The goal of the Winter School was “to introduce participants to current data management best practices for archaeological data and to help them apply these practices to their own circumstances”. The full programme for the ADS Data Stewardship Winter School is provided in Annex 2.

The Winter School was run online via Zoom from the 15th November to the 7th December 2022. The Winter School programme was divided into four interrelated thematic sessions delivered over a

four- week period. The four thematic sessions included: Introducing the ADS, Data management, Digital Preservation and Quality Assurance & Data Reuse

In addition to the ADS training led activities, two additional presentations were organised with special guests from across the UK to provide presentations on topics of interest to the participants (see below). These events allowed the participants to explore some real-world case studies as well as broaden their connections beyond the staff at the ADS.

The Chartered Institute for Archaeologists (Cifa) Dig Digital Toolkits	Dr Manda Foster, DigVentures	Wednesday 23rd November - 1100-1200 GMT
DPC Community Owned Preservation Tools Registry (COPTR) tools	Paul Wheatley, Head of Research and Practice - DPC	Wednesday 23rd November - 1400-1500 GMT

Special presentations for the ADS Data Stewardship Winter School

A number of resources were created during the course that were made available to the participants. As the course was undertaken on Zoom, each of the sessions was recorded, with both the consent of the speakers and course participants. These recordings as well as speakers' PowerPoint presentations were saved in a shared Google drive for later reuse. In addition, a document with an extensive list of links to relevant resources was also produced and provided to course participants.

6 Evaluation and conclusions

In total, ADS were able to provide training for eight candidates, two in 2020 and six in 2022 (one of the Winter School students withdraw at the last minute due to work commitments), fulfilling the target of seven accesses minimum. The 2020 in-house training lasted two days due to the intensity of the subject coverage and the Winter school consisted of four half-day sessions plus two additional hour-long sessions. One advantage of holding the Winter School in separate sessions over several weeks is that the students have time to apply their learning to their projects and ask for further support at the following session should this be necessary.

Following the completion of each call the participants were asked to complete a TNA user feedback report. The form outlined their participation, asked what achievements that they experienced during the training, what difficulties were faced and any suggestions for improvement. The responses have been summarised below but anonymised for data protection reasons.

The feedback report suggested overall that the participants were highly satisfied with the training provided. One participant thanked us for the training and stated that it allowed them to get “a solid background about data management and fundamental knowledge about archiving of digital data”. Another participant stated that they thought the training was “excellent” and that it provided “awareness of the complexity of data preservation for re-use”.

Practical application of the training was visible from participants of the first TNA call. Data management practices learnt from the course were integrated within research projects and consequently digital outputs from these projects are due to be achieved with the ADS in the near future. Participants from the second call have only recently completed their training, however, some immediate outputs were also apparent. Two course participants who are located in the same region, had arranged to meet and collaborate on data stewardship and FAIR data practices. Moreover, another participant believed, based on the information provided, that their institution would implement a new policy on data management and archiving within the next three months.

The resources created and shared from both TNA training activities were well received by participants and reused for both their projects and wider activities. This included PowerPoint presentations, collaboratively produced documents and videos of the presentations from ADS staff members

The main difficulties encountered by the organisers were the restriction to movement encountered due to the COVID pandemic and the difficulty of recruiting sufficient suitable candidates for the training. This was mitigated in the second TNA call by providing the Data Stewardship training online via Zoom to ensure that further delays were not encountered and that a wider group could participate. Some improvements were suggested by course participants in their user feedback forms. One participant suggested the addition of training that would allow them to organise their own workshops and spread the information presented to their colleagues. This was beyond the scope of the TNA training. However, the ADS contacted the participant to offer their services in the future.

There are no plans for follow on activities as this training programme was undertaken at the end of the ARIADNEplus project. However, following the Winter School, further support will be provided by ADS members of staff to all TNA participants on their specific projects if requested.

4 Annexes

1. Guidelines for TNA Evaluators
2. ADS Data Stewardship Winter School Programme

Guidelines for TNA Evaluators

The selection panel is responsible for:

- Assessing the proposals for transnational access received in response to open calls, based on the following selection criteria:
 - o Quality of the applicant,
 - o Scientific merit of the case study or individual research project proposed by the applicant,
 - o Potential benefit to the applicant from the training on offer.
- Applying the principles of transparency, fairness and impartiality to the selection process,
- Attending to gender equality.

Priority will be given to:

- Users who have not previously been awarded ARIADNE resources,
- Early career researchers,
- Researchers working in countries without comparable facilities/opportunities.

Each panel member should indicate his/her evaluation decision by indicating Accept/Reject on the application, providing a short explanation. For positive evaluations, priority should be expressed with a value from one to four (four being the highest score).

The Project Coordinator and the Deputy Coordinator will express the final decision, based on the selection criteria (see above).

Applications from researchers belonging to an ARIADNEplus partner institution are allowed and encouraged, unless they are based on the home country of the institution offering the TNA.

Eligibility criteria (to be checked by the TNA manager)

To be eligible for ARIADNEplus TNA funding, researchers need to comply with the following criteria:

- Work or be registered as a student in an institution in an EU Member State or an Associate State; researchers from institutions in the home country of the TNA opportunity are not eligible to receive an ARIADNEplus TNA bursary.
- Agree to provide feedback on TNA opportunity by:
 - o Completing an ARIADNEplus user report and returning it to TNAcontact@ariadne-infrastructure.eu,
 - o Completing the European Commission's User group questionnaire using the online form.
- Agree to their names being included in a list of ARIADNEplus TNA users provided to the European Commission and published in various media, including the Internet.
- Disseminate results obtained as a result of TNA access as widely as possible and provide ARIADNEplus with the details. Publications should include the following acknowledgement: The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Commission under the H2020 Programme, contract no. H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1-823914 (ARIADNEplus).

ARIADNE Plus Transnational Access Scheme (TNA)

ADS Data Stewardship Winter School

**Course Program
November / December 2022**

Title:	ARIADNE Plus TNA: ADS Data Stewardship Winter School
File name:	ARIADNE TNA schedule_2022.docx
Status:	COMPLETED
Version:	1
Last updated:	07.11.2022
Created date:	17.10.2022
Review due:	N/A
Authors:	Nicky Garland
Maintained by:	Nicky Garland
Required Action:	None

Contents

Data Stewardship	4
Winter School Participants	4
Session 1 - Introducing the ADS	5
Session 2 - Data Management	5
Session 3 - Digital Preservation	7
Session 4 - Quality Assurance & Data Reuse	8
Additional Sessions	9
The ClfA Dig Digital Toolkit	9
Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) Community Owned Preservation Tools Registry (COPTR) tools	10

Data Stewardship

The goal of this Winter School is to introduce participants to current data management best practices for archaeological data and to help them apply these practices to their own circumstances. The course will run over a four week period in November and December 2022.

Each session is designed around four interrelated themes;

- Introducing the ADS
- Data management
- Digital Preservation
- Quality Assurance & Data Reuse

Each session will take place on Zoom. The links to each session are provided below. All times are provided in GMT.

Each week, the presentations will be recorded and available to all participants after each session.

Winter School Participants

- Godefroy Louis François Devevey - Universidade do Algarve
- Dr Vera Moitinho - Institute for the Study of Ancient Culture, Austrian Academy of Sciences
- Dr Solveig Steffen - Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Baden-Württemberg
- Jonas Abele - Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Baden-Württemberg
- Georgina Barrett - Museum of London Archaeology (MOLA)
- Jimmy Maranga - British Institute in Eastern Africa (BIEA)
- Sabina Batlle Baro - University of Barcelona

Session 1 - Introducing the ADS

Date: Tuesday 15th November 2022 - 0900-12.00

<https://york-ac-uk.zoom.us/j/95012055402?pwd=QUttckJDaVpVS2VxbnQwSVpGQ3o4UT09>

In this session we will introduce the work of the ADS and discuss what skills and knowledge participants would like to gain from the Winter School.

Time	Topic	Presenter
09.00 - 09.10 GMT	Welcome to the Data Stewardship Winter School	Dr Holly Wright, Research Projects Manager
09.10 - 09.30	Introduction to the ADS	Dr Tim Evans, Deputy Director
09.30 - 09.50	Attendee introductions	All Attendees
09.50 - 10.10	Discussion - what do you want to get out of the course?	Led by: Dr Holly Wright, Research Projects Manager
10.10 - 10.25	Break	
10.25 - 10.45	Where to start - Knowing and Organising Your Data	Jenny O'Brien, Digital Archivist: Collections and Records
10.45 - 11.05	The FAIR and CARE data principles	Dr Holly Wright, Research Projects Manager
11.05 - 11.25	ADS Guides to Good Practice and ADS Instructions for depositors	Kieron Niven, Digital Archivist: Data Standards
11.25 - 12.00	Final Discussion	Led by: Dr Nicky Garland

Session 2 – Data Management

Date: Wednesday 16th November 2022 – 0900–11.00

<https://york-ac-uk.zoom.us/j/94573785294?pwd=YStkTjQ3bG8zUDFqT2RybEV6YzgzZz09>

In this session we will explore data management planning in more detail including the role of metadata and standardised vocabulary.

Time	Topic	Presenter
09.00 – 09.10 GMT	Welcome and outline of today's sessions	Dr Nicky Garland, Training and Communication Manager
09.10 – 09.40	Introduction to Data Management Planning	Dr Katie Green, Collections Development Manager
09.40 – 09.50	Selection and Retention Strategies	Olivia Foster, Digital Archives Officer
09.50 – 10.05	Break	
10.05 – 10.25	The Importance of Metadata – Discovery and Preservation	Jenny O'Brien, Digital Archivist: Collections and Records
10.25 – 10.45	Introduction to Thesauri and Standardised Vocabulary	Dr Tim Evans, Deputy Director
10.45 – 11.00	Final Discussion	Led by: Dr Nicky Garland

Session 3 – Digital Preservation

Date: Tuesday 22nd November 2022 – 0900–11.30

<https://york-ac-uk.zoom.us/j/95752338083?pwd=TitvTGNORUtoTGFwY3ZnTmFGcTluQT09>

In this session we will explore techniques for digital preservation including data migration and normalisation. We will also provide a look into the digital archiving workflow undertaken by the ADS.

Time	Topic	Presenter
09.00 – 09.10 GMT	Welcome and outline of today's sessions	Dr Nicky Garland, Training and Communications Manager
09.10 – 09.40	Introduction to Digital Preservation	Olivia Foster, Digital Archives Officer
09.40 – 10.00	Migration and Normalisation of Files	Kieron Niven, Digital Archivist: Data Standards
10.00 – 10.15	Break	
10.15 – 10.40	Workflows for Archives – Tour of the ADS archiving workflow	Jenny O'Brien, Digital Archivist: Collections and Records
10.40 – 11.05	Discussion – share your digital archiving workflows	Led by: Dr Nicky Garland and Jenny O'Brien
11.05 – 11.30	Final Discussion	Led by: Dr Nicky Garland

Session 4 – Quality Assurance & Data Reuse

Date: Wednesday 7th December 2022 – 0900-12.00

<https://york-ac-uk.zoom.us/j/99014179530?pwd=ZDIzcEJSQkZoNlVKTmVCNDMlYmIjdz09>

In this final session will look at data quality assurance, providing several case studies. We will finish the Winter School by looking to the future and exploring the benefits of data reuse.

Time	Topic	Presenter
09.00 - 09.10 GMT	Welcome and outline of today's sessions	Dr Nicky Garland, Training and Communication Manager
09.10 - 09.30	Quality Assurance	Kieron Niven, Digital Archivist: Data Standards
09.30 - 09.50	ADS Case study: Monitoring data and data integrity	Kieron Niven, Digital Archivist: Data Standards
09.50 - 10.10	ADS Case study: Where is our Data: Reaching for the clouds	Dr Tim Evans, Deputy Director
10.10 - 10.25	Break	
10.25 - 10.55	Looking to the Future at ADS	Dr Tim Evans, Deputy Director
10.55 - 11.25	Looking to the Future: Data Reuse	Dr Holly Wright, Research Projects Manager
11.25 - 12.00	Final Discussion	Led by: Dr Nicky Garland

Additional Sessions

The sessions below provide additional opportunity for participants to explore specific themes and training requirements. These topics stem from the initial discussion with participants of what topics may be of interest. Each session will last for approximately one hour and will provide participants an opportunity to ask questions of the experts. Sessions are open to all participants.

The ClfA Dig Digital Toolkit

Date: Wednesday 23rd November 2022

<https://york-ac-uk.zoom.us/j/99280443794?pwd=WnVaWnZCQ05ud3hBUGcrR3JDcC9odz09>

The Dig Digital online toolkit was developed by DigVentures in partnership with Chartered Institute for Archaeologists (ClfA). The [toolkit](#) was developed to provide support for those creating digital data in archaeology, helping archaeologists manage digital data and enabling them to produce digital archives that meet professional standards. This talk will be delivered by Dr Manda Foster, who was instrumental in the creation of this resource.

Time	Topic	Presenter
11.00-12.00	Chartered Institute for Archaeologists Dig Digital Toolkit	Dr Manda Forster, DigVentures

Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) Community Owned Preservation Tools Registry (COPTR) tools

Date: Wednesday 23rd November 2022

<https://york-ac-uk.zoom.us/j/94205009156?pwd=SnBkenFEeXdpOXciUUQ3SVVzaWQrQT09>

The [COPTR](#) is one of the most comprehensive registries of digital preservation tools. The register, which was created by and for the international digital preservation community, currently lists more than 500 preservation tools and provides information on functionality, licensing, provenance and user experience.

Time	Topic	Presenter
14.00 - 15.00	DPC COTPR tools	Paul Wheatley, Head of Research and Practice for the Digital Preservation Coalition